

Русский

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Strengthening Civil Society Against Anti-Gender Politics

Research Findings
from the RESIST Project

English

EU Horizon Europe
EU Project
ID 101060749

UK Government
Horizon Europe
Guarantee Scheme

Swiss State Secretariat
for Education, Research
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Deutsch

Why We RESIST

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RESIST studied the rise and impact of 'anti-gender' politics across Europe. This resource presents our findings to a broad audience.

We are a team of researchers interested in how organised attacks on gender equality and LGBTIQ+ rights affect feminists of all genders, LGBTIQ+ people, their communities, and society as a whole. Equally importantly, we have asked: How do feminist and queer people, community groups and organisations resist politically motivated targeting and hostility?

To answer these questions, we spoke with people at the heart of feminist and queer civil society in Europe who have been targeted by 'anti-gender' politics. This included activists, authors, researchers, counsellors, educators, and politicians. We conducted over 250 interviews with people in eight European countries, as well as with exiled individuals who have experienced and actively resisted hostility. In addition, we interviewed 30 civil society experts working on 'anti-gender' politics, and collaborated with 40 civil society organisations, whose insights added valuable perspectives to our research.

We have also analysed how reactionary ideas gain ground in parliaments and media systems across the UK, Switzerland, Poland, Hungary, and in the European Parliament. We examined who is driving these debates and the tactics used to spread dis- and misinformation, stoke fear, and legitimise hate and violence.

What are 'Anti-Gender' Politics?

We use the term 'anti-gender' politics to describe organised opposition, often in the form of attack, to recent social progress in gender equality, reproductive rights, and the rights and representation of LGBTIQ+ people. In RESIST, we do not limit this analysis to the far right. Instead, we examine 'anti-gender' politics across the political spectrum.

This broader perspective is essential because gendered and sexual inequalities continue to shape our societies. Our research shows that 'anti-gender' politics take root in these existing inequalities. Coordinated opposition to women's and LGBTIQ+ rights, along with hostile debates aimed at feminists and queer people, reinforces existing patterns of discrimination.

In recent decades, research in the social sciences and humanities has fundamentally reshaped how we understand gender inequality. Many studies have shown that gender norms are socially and culturally constructed, rather than fixed by nature. The concept of gender has therefore been used to question rigid ideas about the gender binary, gender identity, heterosexuality as the 'natural' foundation of society, and traditional expectations of women's and men's roles and behaviour.

Building on these insights, many current policies aimed at equality and diversity recognise gender inequality as a social issue that can be changed. In response, different political actors have turned the term 'gender' into a political target.

The far right and some conservative and religious actors campaign against the idea of gender, arguing that they are protecting a 'natural order' of society and fixed roles for men and women. In addition, some feminists who describe themselves as 'gender-critical' also defend the idea of biological sex over gender, which they believe should form the basis for feminism. However, this view has been criticised by many feminists as being exclusionary of trans women and non-binary people.

In RESIST, we distance ourselves from this political targeting of gender and therefore single quote 'anti-gender' to indicate that it is used critically.

Through RESIST, we have examined ‘anti-gender’ politics from an intersectional perspective. In our case studies, we explored how ‘anti-gender’ politics intersect with racist and anti-immigration politics and how they affect multiply marginalised groups, for example, queer people who are also racialised or are migrants.

Why Intersectionality Matters

👉 Intersectionality is central to our research. The term emerged from the social movements of Black women and women of colour in Europe and the US, who challenged how sexism and racism work together to shape their lives. Since then, it has become a key feminist and anti-racist concept worldwide.

👉 Intersectionality helps activists and researchers understand how different forms of inequality, such as gender, sexuality, race, class, and disability, interact and influence both people’s everyday experiences and how discrimination operates.

👉 It also helps identify who is included or excluded in struggles for equality, revealing marginalisation even within feminist and anti-racist movements. In RESIST, we use intersectionality to explore how ‘anti-gender’ politics affect feminists and LGBTIQ+ people who are multiply marginalised. We found that those who are migrants, experience racism, or live with a disability are particularly vulnerable to ‘anti-gender’ politics as they often lack access to inclusive feminist or queer communities.

About RESIST

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RESIST is a research project involving queer and feminist researchers from ten institutions across Europe. We are all committed to social justice and academic rigour. To understand the complex workings of 'anti-gender' politics, we drew upon insights from sociology, human geography, philosophy, gender studies, anthropology, and cultural studies.

How to Use This Resource:

- I Understand common strategies and tactics used by 'anti-gender' actors.
- II Recognise effects on individuals, communities, and democracy.
- III Explore how individuals, communities and organisations resist.
- IV Use questions for reflection and discussion to counter 'anti-gender' politics.

10

About
RESIST

Guide to Resistance

11

Inside the 'Anti-Gender' Playbook. What Media and Parliamentary Politics Reveal 12

Who is Behind 'Anti-Gender' Politics?

Strategies and Tactics

What Narratives Are Used?

Lives Under Attack. How 'Anti-Gender' Politics Are Felt on the Ground 26

What Do Feminists and LGBTIQ+ People Experience?

What Are the Effects on Individuals, Communities and Democracy?

Strategies from Everyday Feminist and Queer Resistance 46

How Individuals Resist

How Communities Resist 'Anti-Gender' Politics and Build Pluralistic Futures

Questions for Discussion and Reflection 66

Explore More RESIST Resources 72

Inside the 'Anti-Gender' Playbook

What Media and
Parliamentary
Politics Reveal

EU Horizon Europe
EU Project
ID 101060749

UK Government
Horizon Europe
Guarantee Scheme

12
Swiss State Secretariat
for Education, Research
and Innovation

13

Inside the
'Anti-Gender'
Playbook.
What Media and
Parliamentary
Politics Reveal

Across parliaments and media landscapes in Hungary, Poland, Switzerland, the UK, and in the European Parliament, our data unveils recurring and coordinated attacks that are deeply rooted in societal inequalities.

Overall, we found that:

- I **Women's and LGBTQ+ rights are increasingly being eroded and rolled back.**
- II **Public discourse is growing more hostile toward trans people.**

But who is driving these narratives? How do they gain traction? And why do they resonate?

16

Inside the
'Anti-Gender'
Playbook.
What Media and
Parliamentary
Politics Reveal

Who is Behind 'Anti-Gender' Politics?

17

Our analysis of parliamentary debates in the UK, European, Swiss, Hungarian, and Polish Parliaments shows that 'anti-gender' debates are largely driven by male politicians from conservative and far-right parties.

An exception is the European Parliament, where both men and women MEPs actively promote 'anti-gender' views. An 'anti-gender' agenda is common among men and women politicians in the Identity and Democracy (ID) and European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR) groups.

However, other actors drive 'anti-gender' politics too:

- I **In both Switzerland and Poland, 'anti-gender' messaging is amplified not only by the right but also by centrist politicians.**
- II **In the UK, some opponents of trans rights identify as feminists.**
- III **A fast-paced, competitive media environment thrives on controversy and sensationalism, encouraging outlets to spread anti-trans narratives.**
- IV **Across contexts, right-wing media promote the idea of a so-called 'gender ideology', making it a recurring source of public controversy that is often echoed by broadsheet media.**

Research Spotlight. Constructing Controversy

Trans Politics in the UK Media

- R** Our analysis of three UK newspapers (The Guardian, The Telegraph, and The Scotsman) revealed that coverage of trans issues has become a central part of right-wing media 'culture wars'. In this context, trans people are often directly targeted, and debates about gender and sexuality are advanced as part of a larger social or political conspiracy.
- R** By doing so, these actors flood media spaces with anti-trans messages, making them seem more widespread and credible. In this environment, sensational and provocative stories spark attention and clicks. This is not merely about ideology; it is also about profit. Outlets like GB News use controversy to attract viewers and revenue, often without adhering to traditional journalistic standards.
- R** This pattern is especially visible in The Telegraph, which frequently publishes critical and hostile stories about trans people. Our findings suggest that this is part of a wider right-wing media network, including outlets like GB News and groups such as the Free Speech Union, that share and repeat each other's content.
- R** These media platforms also present themselves as 'defenders of free speech', claiming that support for anti-discrimination limits expression. This argument feeds into a broader story that paints 'gender ideology' as censorship, while portraying anti-trans coverage as courageous and truth-telling.

Strategies and Tactics

20

Inside the
'Anti-Gender'
Playbook.
What Media and
Parliamentary
Politics Reveal

While 'anti-gender' strategies are shaped by local contexts, our analysis shows that they also follow common transnational patterns. Here are three key 'anti-gender' tactics that appear across multiple countries.

Weaponising Language. The Use of Cyphers

'Anti-gender' actors often use vague but emotionally charged words and phrases, which we call cyphers, to advance their agendas. A cypher is a term that is strategically chosen in political debates to signal threats or enemies. In the context of 'anti-gender' politics, we have identified several terms that work in this way:

'Gender ideology' is one of the most common examples of such a cypher. Its meaning shifts across contexts, but it is always loaded and invokes a threat.

- I In the UK, the term is mainly used in anti-trans discourse.
- II In Poland and Hungary, it is used to undermine reproductive rights, LGBTIQ+ visibility, and comprehensive sexuality education.

This flexibility of cyphers is strategic: by blurring different issues, 'gender ideology' is framed as a broad danger to society. Its vagueness makes it hard to challenge in public debates.

Strategies
and Tactics

21

Another cypher is the term 'sexualisation', which also varies by context.

- I In Poland, it is used by 'anti-gender' actors to oppose trans people's autonomy, feminist perspectives, LGBTIQ+ activism, sexual education, and women's rights.
- II In Switzerland, it vilifies comprehensive sexuality education and gender-affirming healthcare for trans youth.

This tactical use of language helps 'anti-gender' actors adapt their messaging to different settings and audiences, while benefiting from the same loaded terms to undermine a range of rights and democratic struggles.

Political Opportunism

Rather than following a unified strategy, 'anti-gender' politics thrive on incoherence and opportunism. This makes them flexible, unpredictable, and hard to counter.

- I Tactics shift quickly depending on political opportunities. For example, when progressive laws are proposed, 'anti-gender' actors mobilise in response.
- II Campaigns often cross ideological lines, forming unusual alliances united only by opposition to specific gender or sexuality issues. This is especially visible in attacks on trans rights.

This incoherence gives 'anti-gender' actors a political advantage: they can adapt rapidly, reframe their narratives when opportune, and mobilise support from across the political spectrum. It also makes them unpredictable.

Media Controversies as a Strategy for Visibility
'Anti-gender' actors use the media to generate controversy and amplify their narratives.

- I **They provoke debates on topics that are deemed controversial (e.g., trans rights, comprehensive sexuality education) to dominate the news cycle.**
- II **Sensationalism becomes the main tool for visibility.**
- III **In today's fast-paced media landscape, loud, controversial voices gain more attention, even when their claims lack evidence.**
- IV **By repeating similar content across platforms, 'anti-gender' actors saturate public debates around these topics, making harmful narratives seem more credible.**

This tactic is not only about gaining attention. It is also about shaping public opinion through constant visibility and repetition, even if that involves spreading misleading or inaccurate claims.

What Narratives Are Used?

'Anti-gender' actors do not present themselves as discriminatory; instead, they frame their arguments in the language of democracy and rights.

Inventing a Threat

Gender, feminism, and LGBTIQ+ rights are portrayed as threats to children, families, and national values. Rights claims by feminist and LGBTIQ+ civil society are presented as attacks on freedom, tradition, or societal stability.

This framing breeds fear and not only justifies opposition to equality and inclusion but also acts as a catalyst for hate and violence.

Democratic Language as a Weapon

'Anti-gender' actors use the language of rights and freedoms to position themselves as defenders of democracy, while undermining the rights of others.

Democratic values and rights like pluralism, parental rights, and academic freedom are co-opted to oppose gender equality and LGBTIQ+ inclusion.

- I **In Hungary, parental rights are invoked to justify laws banning discussion of LGBTIQ+ issues in schools, presenting state censorship as the democratic empowerment of families.**
- II **In Poland, freedom of religion is cited to justify restrictions on reproductive rights and LGBTIQ+ visibility, framing 'anti-gender' policies as the protection of traditional values.**

Freedom of speech is used to justify 'anti-gender' and anti-trans rhetoric, framing harmful discourse as a right to express 'unpopular opinions'.

I For example, in the UK, campaigns against so-called 'cancel culture' portray 'gender-critical' views as silenced truths that need protection.

This strategy lends anti-equality agendas a veneer of legitimacy, making them harder to challenge without appearing anti-democratic.

Defending Society

'Anti-gender' actors claim to protect democracy, children, and families from so-called 'excesses' of gender equality and sexual rights.

I In Switzerland and the UK, they depict feminism and LGBTIQ+ rights as having 'gone too far', threatening social cohesion or common-sense values.

II In Hungary and Poland, feminist and queer civil society organisations are accused of being a foreign influence that undermines national values, of not representing 'ordinary people', and of being anti-democratic by claiming rights at the expense of the majority.

These narratives are used to delegitimise civil society and justify restrictions on activism. They also serve to shrink civic space under the guise of defending national identity and democratic order.

Considering these alarming developments in politics and media debates, our project explored how civil society is affected. We therefore asked: How do queer and feminist people experience the impact of these coordinated attacks on their rights, identities, and lives?

Lives Under Attack

How 'Anti-Gender' Politics Are Felt on the Ground

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26
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Lives Under
Attack.
How 'Anti-Gender'
Politics Are Felt on
the Ground

INDOCTRINATION!
PROPAGANDA!

We have spoken to over 250 feminist and queer individuals across eight European countries—Belarus, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Poland, Spain, and Switzerland—as well as with exiled intellectuals from Turkey. They shared how coordinated ‘anti-gender’ campaigns affect their everyday lives. Additionally, we interviewed 30 experts from civil society organisations and academia, selected for their longstanding professional expertise in areas including human rights and gender-based violence.

Our participants include public figures (such as politicians, activists, authors, and researchers), educators and counsellors, sex workers, and members of the broader queer and feminist civil society.

There are, of course, differences across the contexts studied. Yet in all case studies, participants explained that organised attacks on feminists and LGBTIQ+ people rely on longstanding discrimination. When certain identities are already seen as less valid, ‘anti-gender’ narratives spread more easily.

‘Anti-gender’ politics do not only come from the far right or conservative circles; it can also be found in parts of the left, and even among some feminist and lesbian-gay communities. These actors often target trans people, sex workers, and those who advocate for intersectional approaches.

The data we collected shows that legal protections alone are not enough to shield people from ‘anti-gender’ politics. Across countries, participants noted that international law is often not implemented in ways that meaningfully improve their lives. In some places, progressive laws exist on paper but are undermined by new reactionary laws passed simultaneously.

This section maps the types of attacks faced by the feminist and LGBTIQ+ individuals we interviewed across all case studies.

30

Lives Under
Attack.
How ‘Anti-Gender’
Politics Are Felt on
the Ground

What Do Feminists and LGBTIQ+ People Experience?

31

Political Vilification and Misrepresentation

Manufactured
controversies

Media, religious, and political actors often stage debates that exclude those directly targeted by ‘anti-gender’ politics, giving platforms instead to ‘anti-gender’ actors and reinforcing one-sided narratives and misinformation. Trans people in particular reported feeling hyper-visible in these hostile debates while receiving little meaningful representation in media or politics.

Distorted
representation
of trans and
feminist voices

LGBTIQ+ people, particularly trans individuals and feminist activists, are often talked about in public debates without being given the opportunity to speak for themselves. Those who conform to stereotypes or express reactionary views are sometimes used as tokens to fuel controversy. Many queer and feminist people feel that their perspectives are filtered through reactionary political or media agendas rather than expressed in their own words.

Mocking language
and misgendering
in media and
political discourse

Controversies around inclusive language and pronouns, alongside pronoun misuse in public discourse, turn trans and non-binary people into targets of ridicule rather than subjects with rights.

Multiply marginalised people are accused of divisive politics

Feminist and queer communities often face challenges in openly discussing racism in relation to gender equality and LGBTIQ+ rights. Migrant and racialised participants described encountering racist stereotypes, hostility, or dismissal when expressing their experiences and needs.

Use of Law to Restrict Feminist and LGBTIQ+ People

Attacks on reproductive and trans rights

In several countries, political and religious actors open debates intending to roll back reproductive rights and block legal reforms on liberalising abortion, access to reproductive health services, and simplifying gender recognition and parenthood for same-gender couples. In some countries, the proposition of new progressive policies can also spark reactionary pressure and violence against those who support such new legislation.

State-level repression of gender diversity and equality efforts

Political repression is experienced to varying degrees across different countries. This includes banning pride marches and events, prohibiting feminist posters in public, and preventing public institutions from using queer-inclusive, gender-neutral language. In some contexts, state-level repression also extends to surveillance and arrest of activists.

Instrumental use of parliamentary procedures

Politicians submit parliamentary questions to scrutinise and delegitimise the existence of initiatives and question the funding of feminist and LGBTIQ+ projects.

Legal intimidation

Strategic lawsuits against public participation (SLAPPs) are used to silence and exhaust feminist and queer activists, organisations, academics, and authors, especially those speaking out in public debates or challenging 'anti-gender' narratives.

Threatening Feminist and LGBTIQ+ Professionals and Institutions

Workplace punishment and reputation threats

Public-facing individuals, such as educators, activists, and academics, face professional consequences and disciplinary measures for supporting feminist or queer issues. These include dismissal, threats to job security, disciplinary actions, negative performance reviews, and reputational damage.

Organisational targeting

Feminist and LGBTIQ+ organisations are subjected to formal scrutiny through politically motivated inspections and freedom of information requests. The participants also reported orchestrated threats by email, phone, and online platforms. Some organisations have faced physical attacks on their offices and premises, while others experience public harassment, such as protests staged outside their buildings. SLAPPs are used as a tool to silence and burden activists and professionals with legal costs.

Intimidation of academics

Academics are confronted with attempts to influence their work through delegitimisation and intimidation, both from within and outside of academia, including from senior church figures. Academics are targets of media and social media pressure campaigns, as well as coordinated letter-writing efforts aimed at cutting research funding. Some receive personal threats, and others have lost their positions.

Targeted attacks on educators and educational initiatives

Parliamentarians have sought to ban teaching on gender- and sexuality-related issues. Politically motivated actors infiltrate schools, while external campaigns distribute leaflets to discredit inclusive education. Closed workshops are disrupted, and educators face threats, lawsuits, and smear campaigns for supporting equality-focused teaching.

**Digital Danger, Physical Risk.
The Cost of Speaking Out****Digital violence**

Many of our interviewed participants and their organisations have experienced coordinated harassment, cyber-attacks on websites, and doxing—the publishing of private details such as personal address to intimidate victims. Cyberbullying often involves hate speech, mass reporting, amplification of visibility by high-profile accounts, and being named on public target lists.

Harassment and surveillance

Individuals, especially women and trans people who have a public platform, reported facing verbal abuse, threats, intimidation, surveillance, stalking, and targeted sexualised hate speech.

Pride protests under threat

LGBTIQ+ participants recounted how public events like Pride marches are regularly disrupted by far-right groups, including neo-Nazis, aiming to intimidate and suppress advocacy.

Physical violence

Feminists and LGBTIQ+ people we interviewed have also experienced assault, including attacks in their place of residence, sometimes involving weapons, and in certain contexts, abuse by law enforcement. Multiply marginalised participants reported being particularly vulnerable to physical attacks. Trans women who are refugees recounted being exposed to violence in refugee camps without anyone to turn to for protection. Disabled trans and non-binary people experience fear of leaving their home due to the physical violence they have experienced. The felt increase in assaults also contributes to an environment of rising insecurity among entire communities.

What Are the Effects on Individuals, Communities, and Democracy?

36

Lives Under
Attack.
How 'Anti-Gender'
Politics Are Felt on
the Ground

Our study demonstrates that the effects of 'anti-gender' politics intensify existing discrimination against women and LGBTIQ+ people. These organised attacks worsen inequity because women and LGBTIQ+ people are already underrepresented in political institutions and lack equitable access to the media agenda.

'Anti-gender' politics further silence minority voices and operate alongside existing hostility towards feminist and queer movements. They threaten civil society by reinforcing the persistent underfunding of feminist and LGBTIQ+ organisations.

Our research findings show that the impact of 'anti-gender' politics is particularly severe for people who are multiply marginalised, such as refugees, people of colour, and people living with disabilities. They experience unequal access to decision-making, resources and influence within feminist and LGBTIQ+ communities.

This section outlines how 'anti-gender' politics impact individuals, communities, and democracy.

What Are
the Effects on
Individuals,
Communities,
and Democracy?

37

Psychosocial Effects

'Anti-gender' attacks have a chilling effect

Many participants shared that the threat of attacks or legal consequences has pushed them to withdraw from public debate and visible roles in society.

Burnout and disillusionment

Constant public vilification can lead to profound exhaustion, burnout, and political disillusionment, often causing individuals to step back from activism or community work.

Lack of support for those who are multiply marginalised

People who face multiple forms of marginalisation report feeling unsupported, even within feminist and LGBTIQ+ spaces. As a result, some feel they have nowhere to turn and disengage from these communities.

Impact of forced migration

Those who migrated due to 'anti-gender' hostility experience displacement, isolation, and a loss of social status and professional standing. In addition, they must navigate racism and anti-immigration sentiment.

Abandoned in the aftermath

Victims of targeted attacks frequently describe feeling abandoned, not just by law enforcement, but also by employers or funders when attacks are linked to their work. Many have had to rely on personal resources to cope with the consequences.

TIME
IS
RUNNING

Effects on Communities and Organisations

Spaces become harder to access

Community services and spaces become more hidden and harder to access for service users, as advertising them publicly risks backlash or attack.

Resources are stretched thin

Organisations are forced to spend increasing time and energy resources managing the effects of attacks, dealing with threats, rebuilding trust, and improving security, whilst also continuing to focus on their core work and support their communities.

Funding dries up as demand grows

Demand for services is growing, but many organisations are losing funding, either because political support disappears or funders fear being drawn into controversy.

Exclusion within communities

Harmful narratives about trans and non-binary people, sex workers, refugees, or people of colour can sometimes take hold within feminist and queer spaces. These narratives exclude those who are at the margins of communities or who face intersecting forms of discrimination.

Internal conflict weakens solidarity

Tensions across generations, political perspectives, and a failure to address discrimination within communities can escalate into open hostility. As a result, solidarity fractures, disillusionment grows, and some disengage from their communities altogether.

Effects on Democracy

Violence becomes normalised

The growing use of threats, harassment, and legal intimidation against feminists and LGBTIQ+ people discourages participation in public life and obstructs open, democratic debate.

Harmful narratives go mainstream

Reactionary ideas are increasingly accepted as 'common sense', making it easier to justify repression and more difficult to challenge discrimination.

Rights work is discredited

'Anti-gender' actors frame feminism and LGBTIQ+ advocacy as threats to children, religion, or society, rather than as legitimate human rights work. This shrinks civic space and weakens democracy.

Media and political debates distort reality

Media debates do not give substantive representation of feminists and LGBTIQ+ people. Staged controversies dominate public discourse. Trans and queer people are often spoken about instead of being heard, while stereotypes and misinformation replace facts and lived experience.

Academic freedom is under threat

Scholars face pressure from political actors and risk losing funding or safety if they research gender or sexuality. Some avoid public engagement or censor themselves out of fear.

Exclusion of multiply marginalised voices exacerbates

Migrants, people of colour, and disabled people face additional barriers to participation, even within feminist and LGBTIQ+ spaces, limiting inclusive, democratic decision-making.

Civic education is undermined

'Anti-gender' actors actively block educational efforts that foster understanding of gender and sexuality, threatening long-term democratic engagement and literacy.

The effects of 'anti-gender' politics documented in our interviews are dramatic, and reveal what is at stake for European civil society. The next section explores how feminists and LGBTIQ+ people transform intimidation into action, isolation into connection, and attacks into collective strength.

What Are the Effects on Individuals, Communities, and Democracy?

Strategies from Everyday Feminist and Queer Resistance

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Our data shows that civil society is the backbone of the resistance against 'anti-gender' politics.

Together with 40 organisations across Europe, and drawing on our research data, we explored how feminist and queer organisations and communities resist, build solidarity, and defend themselves against ongoing attacks on their rights, safety, and lives.

In a context of dwindling resources and growing demand, individuals, community groups, and organisations mobilise solidarity, form networks, and foster connections with journalists, politicians, the private sector, and society at large.

50

Strategies
from
Everyday
Feminist
and Queer
Resistance

51

How Individuals Resist

| Building connections

Many individuals resist by finding strength in community, whether locally or online. Feeling supported and experiencing solidarity helps individuals cope with attacks and growing hostility that they face.

For those who were forced to migrate due to 'anti-gender' politics, supportive spaces offer environments for open advocacy and political expression.

II Everyday acts of resistance

Feminist and LGBTIQ+ people claim space by making their identities visible in public or private settings.

Speaking up in daily life, at work, with family, or among friends, is seen as a powerful way of pushing back against ‘anti-gender’ narratives.

Personal conversations, sharing lived experiences, and creating space for open dialogue can foster empathy and prevent extremist views from taking root.

When dialogue is not possible or safe, some choose to set clear boundaries, take a firm stand, or actively refuse to engage with harmful narratives.

III Self-protection as resistance

Although claiming visibility is seen as important, for those under intense scrutiny or threat, such as trans people and migrants, strategically reducing visibility or even choosing anonymity can be an act of survival.

In highly repressive environments, secrecy is viewed as a form of protecting oneself and resisting state or societal control.

IV Claiming public space

Despite risks, some activists and academics choose public visibility as resistance, taking up space, staying vocal, and continuing their work publicly. This choice, however, is deeply shaped by one's social position, privilege, and access to resources, making solidarity and support networks essential.

How Communities Resist 'Anti-Gender' Politics and Build Pluralistic Futures

56

Strategies
from
Everyday
Feminist
and Queer
Resistance

I Building services and support

Civil society organisations and community groups create lifelines of care and protection—often without funding—by:

Offering peer-led psychosocial support services.

Helping people navigate legal challenges through accessible legal counselling.

57

How
Communities
Resist
'Anti-Gender'
Politics
and Build
Pluralistic
Futures

Conducting safety audits and developing protocols for spaces, events, and online platforms, sometimes working with law enforcement to keep everyone safer.

Hosting community-led classes on digital safety, advocacy skills, and self-defence to empower individuals directly.

Capacity building in digital campaigning and strategic social media use to reach the general public.

II Creating spaces of solidarity

Resistance grows strongest in spaces where people feel seen in their identities, heard in their experiences, and supported by those around them:

Organisations and groups facilitate safe, welcoming community spaces for those targeted by ‘anti-gender’ politics to connect, share, and organise.

Some groups and organisations adopt an intersectional perspective to make sure their structures meet the needs of those often left out, especially multiply marginalised members, by creating dedicated spaces and platforms for their voices. This inclusion is considered crucial for fostering sustainable democratic dialogue within communities.

They also encourage open, intergenerational conversations that bridge divides and nurture pluralistic perspectives. These dialogues help resolve conflicts and build a culture of respect, trust, and collaboration.

III Building stronger networks and collaborations

Our research participants agree—resistance is stronger when it is connected, strategic, and wide-reaching:

Civil society organisations collaborate with journalists committed to accurate, respectful reporting to challenge harmful stereotypes, and amplify stories and expertise from communities.

They create professional support networks for educators, journalists, researchers and people working and volunteering in civil society organisations. Such networks provide support during and in the aftermath of attacks. They serve as spaces for peer support, resource sharing, and coordinated responses, including collaboration with funders and institutions to mitigate attacks.

They form transnational alliances between individuals and organisations that pool resources, share knowledge, and amplify advocacy efforts beyond national borders, which is seen as beneficial.

Scholars engage politicians and government actors to share evidence, and civil society organisations raise awareness and secure funding for essential services and initiatives.

Civil society organisations deem it important to build relationships with politicians, media personalities, artists, and businesses to foster broad-based allyship and mobilise wider public support.

IV **Protesting and celebrating collectively**

Resistance is not just about pushing back; it is also about joy, visibility, and reclaiming power. Our research data illustrates that in the face of 'anti-gender' politics, those attacked find relief in:

Joining forces across communities to respond swiftly and powerfully to 'anti-gender' attacks by shaping the narrative; telling their own stories, on their terms.

Organising collective protests, counter-protests, creative public actions, and pride events that claim visibility and empower participants.

Prioritising joyful gatherings where community members celebrate resilience, build friendships, and recharge their spirit, because joy fuels the long fight for justice.

Questions for Discussion and Reflection

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These questions encourage reflection and discussion on how individuals, communities, and organisations can respond to and counter 'anti-gender' politics. Examples may come from this brochure, your own experience, or wider practice.

68

Questions
for
Discussion
and Reflection

Learning from practice

Which examples, from this brochure or your own experience, show effective ways of responding to 'anti-gender' politics?

How are the voices of people facing multiple forms of disadvantage included or excluded in these responses?

69

What lessons can help improve collaboration between different sectors in responding to 'anti-gender' mobilisations, including civil society, government, media, education, research, healthcare, business, faith-based organisations, and cultural actors?

II Roles and responsibilities

What roles can professionals in these fields, including policymakers, journalists, civil society organisations, educators, healthcare providers, businesses, and cultural or faith-based institutions, play in supporting inclusive and democratic responses to ‘anti-gender’ politics?

How can joint initiatives ensure that those most affected, including people facing multiple forms of discrimination, will have influence in shaping solutions?

Explore More RESIST Resources

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Guarantee Scheme

72
Swiss State Secretariat
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73

All RESIST resources are available on the [RESIST website](#) and [project repository](#), offering evidence, guidance, and interactive tools for journalists, policy-makers, and civil society.

RESIST/ANCE. Strategies for a Better World

An interactive, collaborative serious game for 2-3 players (or larger workshops) that helps participants explore how ‘anti-gender’ mobilisations operate, their real-world impacts, and strategies to resist them. RESIST/ANCE provides a safe space to learn, reflect, and act together. The game is available for free. For more information, visit the RESIST project website.

For Journalists. The Role of Media in European Anti-Gender Politics

A deep dive into how media shapes ‘anti-gender’ politics across Europe. This resource provides detailed analyses for journalists to understand how ‘anti-gender’ politics take hold of media debates.

For Policy Makers. Policy Brief and Policy Recommendations

A summary of our findings highlighting the impact of ‘anti-gender’ politics, and concrete recommendations for policies and interventions that support inclusive and democratic responses across Europe.

Research Reports

Detailed reports presenting the project’s methodologies, case studies, and in-depth analysis of ‘anti-gender’ politics across Europe.

Solidarity and Struggle. Resisting Anti-Gender Politics

A free self-paced online course aimed at non-specialist, general audience learners. Using interactive activities, it conveys the findings of the RESIST Project and other research about ‘anti-gender’ mobilisations.

For all materials and downloads, visit the **RESIST website and project repository.**

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Title

**Strengthening Civil Society
Against Anti-Gender Politics**

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Contributors

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Other Info

Project Deliverable D4.1:

Tools for stakeholders including policy recommendations. Work Package 4 - Re-invigorating Feminist Theories.

Outputs repository

zenodo.org/communities/resistproject

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theresistproject.eu

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